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Investigation of Single Pass Shape Rolling Using an Upper Bound

Method

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Abstract

This paper presents a generalized analytical upper bound method for the study of deformation, pressure and torque in the single pass rolling of shaped sections. Generalized kinematically admissible velocity fields have been calculated from an assumed deforming geometry, in turn mathematically developed from the parameterization of curves for the stream line flow of the material. An upper bound on rolling power was established based on the calculated velocity fields. Unknown variables in the velocity field were determined by minimizing rolling power with respect to unknown velocity field variables, yielding an upper limit to the actual power required as well as rolling pressure and torque. As an applied example the single oval-to-round and rectangle-to-diamond roll passes have been chosen and analyzed. Velocity fields and power relations were obtained for each pass and computer analysis was carried out to analyze and simulate the process of shape rolling. Deformation, average roll torque and rolling pressure data from the analysis were compared with other worker's analytical solutions, numerical analyses and experimental data. The results were found to be in good agreement with previous research and the method was shown to be quicker and easier to use.

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Introduction

The rolling of shaped section in industry has always been a difficult process to control and the influence of process parameters on the production is of great interest. Although finite element analysis could be used to analyze and simulate such processes but there are several serious drawbacks in using finite element method. Firstly modeling and simulation process which is very time consuming and difficult should be carried over every time the shape of the rolled part is changed. Due to large deformations involved in shape rolling and the distortion of elements in FEM, convergence of the result becomes an issue which sometimes is impossible to deal with and other times takes a lot of the time and memory of the computer. However analytical methods such as upper bound if properly developed could be applied to such problems with ease and get to the results in a comparatively short time. The most important advantage of the upper bound method used in this paper is that it is formulated in a general manner so that any process of shape rolling could be dealt with and analyzed.

On the other hand a complicated three dimensional material flow takes place in the rolling of shapes and therefore its analysis involves large numbers of process variables, the determination of which becomes more difficult with increasing complexity of the rolled section. As a result, empirical formulae have been developed for the design of pass sequences and the prediction of roll load and torque as well as entry and exit velocities. These formulae are limited to conventional materials and rolling conditions [1,2].

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With the advancement of industry, however, new shapes and materials evolve for which the creation of empirical roll pass design and other rolling parameters requires extensive experimentation.

Due to the difficulty of analytical solutions of rolling, most research in this field is focused on numerical approaches. Analytical studies have been scarce and mainly limited to specific passes. The most authoritative analytical work on rolling has been carried out by Kennedy [3]. He developed an upper bound method for the analysis of metal deformation and stresses in the rolling of both flat sections and geometrical profiles without protrusions based on the general velocity fields proposed by Hill [4]. Saito et al proposed an upper bound method that was capable of predicting lateral spread, elongation and thickness in flat, concave (diamond) and convex (box) passes [5]. Bayoumi used a flow-line field solution to analyze material flow and stresses in the steady-state rolling of the round-oval-round rolling sequence [6].

The finite element method - FEM - has been used extensively to study both flat and shape rolling. A pioneering research work was carried out by Oh and Kobayashi who used the extremum principle for rigid, perfectly plastic materials in combination with numerical analysis to investigate side spread in flat rolling [7]. Since then, several other researchers have used three dimensional FEM for analyzing spread in rolling [8-10]. Park and Oh developed a rigid-plastic 3D FEM code for the analysis of shape rolling processes, which is capable of handling arbitrary cross-sections [10]. Mori and Osakada [11,12] developed a rigid-plastic 3D FEM to simulate steady-state deformation in shape rolling with grooved rolls. Kim and Altan combined the two-dimensional rigid-plastic finite element method with the slab method to reduce the amount of computation without losing accuracy [13]. Hsiang, Lin developed a piece-wise complex model

Pre-print of: [Karen Abrinia](#) & A. Fazlirad (2010). Investigation of Single Pass Shape Rolling Using an Upper Bound Method. Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance. DOI: [10.1007/s11665-009-9511-x](#) combining the slab and finite element methods. They divided the deformation zone into several slabs and used FEM to calculate sequentially the velocity field, metal flow, stress and strain distribution for each slab [14].

The development of an analytical, theoretically-based method to predict metal flow, roll torque, rolling pressure and force and exit velocity for shape rolling is of great benefit to the rolling industry. Such a method for the analysis of the rolling of simple geometrical shapes including oval, round, rectangle and diamond sections has been presented in this study. The analysis assumes the material is rigid, perfectly plastic, and does not consider combined thermo-mechanical effects. A new parametric formulation has been proposed to cover the entire deformation zone, based on which strain rates and velocities are determined. The oval-to-round and diamond-to-rectangle passes have been analyzed with the new method.

Theory

Geometry of the deformation zone

The material under the action of the rolls deforms from its original shape (oval or rectangular in this paper) to a final shaped section (round and diamond, respectively, in this paper). Deformation occurs within a bounded region as shown in Fig. 1 for a general case. It can be seen from the figure that entry and exit cross sections have been chosen as arbitrarily shaped and considered as plane surfaces. The other bounding surfaces of the deforming region are the roll surfaces. This geometry has been defined using parametric curve definitions. It is based on the choice of a streamline BB' and a

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stream surface OAA'O' (Fig.1). The entry and exit sections are represented by OCD

and OC'D' respectively. To simplify relations, a left-hand coordinate system has been employed.

Fig. 1- A quarter of the deformation zone considered for shape rolling analysis

It has been assumed that the deformation zone consists of such stream surfaces as

OAA'O' within which streamlines such as BB' are located. It has been further

assumed that any given particle P in the deformation zone travels on such streamlines

and the proportionality relation $\frac{OB}{OA} = \frac{O'B'}{O'A'}$ holds true along the entire trajectory. This

assumption presents a method to mathematically define the deformation zone in the

shape rolling of an arbitrary section to another arbitrary section [15]. Streamlines have

been described with Bezier's parametric curve formulation [16].

A typical cubic Bezier curve is defined by

$$\vec{r}(t) = (1-t)^3 \vec{V}_0 + 3t(1-t)^2 \vec{V}_1 + 3t^2(1-t) \vec{V}_2 + t^3 \vec{V}_3 \quad (1)$$

Or in matrix notation

$$\vec{r}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & t & t^2 & t^3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -3 & 3 & -2 & -1 \\ 2 & -2 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{V}_0 \\ \vec{V}_1 \\ \vec{V}_2 \\ \vec{V}_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where \vec{V}_0 through \vec{V}_3 mark the position vectors of the control points of the Bezier

curve, $0 \leq t \leq 1$ is the main curve defining parameter and $\vec{r}(t)$ is the position vector of

any given point on the curve.

Expressing streamlines within the deformation zone as Bezier curves requires that

position vectors be appropriately defined. In the present paper, the following general format has been chosen for the vectors.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{V}_0 &= F_0(u, q)\vec{i} + G_0(u, q)\vec{j} \\
 \vec{V}_1 &= a_1F_0(u, q)\vec{i} + b_1G_0(u, q)\vec{j} + c_1H_0(u, q)\vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}_2 &= a_2F_1(u, q)\vec{i} + b_2G_1(u, q)\vec{j} + c_2H_1(u, q)\vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}_3 &= F_1(u, q)\vec{i} + G_1(u, q)\vec{j} + H_1(u, q)\vec{k}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Where F_0 and G_0 are functions that determine the location of point B (Fig. 1) and its position vector \vec{V}_0 , F_1 and G_1 the location of B' and position vector \vec{V}_3 , H_0 and H_1 the position of the Bezier tangent vectors. a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, c_1 and c_2 are arbitrary coefficients that help determine the position of control points. \vec{V}_0 and \vec{V}_3 are the position vectors of points B and B' respectively; \vec{V}_1 and \vec{V}_2 are the tangent vectors at these points. F_0 through H_1 have been assumed as functions of two other parameters u and q where $0 \leq u, q \leq 1$.

Combining equations 1 and 3 yields the fundamental position vector utilized in this study:

$$\vec{r} = f(u, q, t)\vec{i} + g(u, q, t)\vec{j} + h(u, q, t)\vec{k} \tag{4}$$

And in the Cartesian coordinate system:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x &= f(u, q, t) \\
 y &= g(u, q, t) \\
 z &= h(u, q, t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Generalized kinematically-admissible velocity field

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The procedure outlined in the present study is based on the upper bound method of analysis [17]. In order to apply the upper bound method to metal forming operations, it is first necessary to determine kinematically-admissible velocity fields based on an assumption of the shape of the streamlines in the deformation zone.

The velocity field was found by equating the unit tangent vector for the point P (\vec{r} differentiated with respect to parameter t) on the streamline BB' (Fig. 1) to the unit velocity vector.

The unit velocity vector is represented by

$$\vec{V} = \frac{(V_x \cdot \vec{i} + V_y \cdot \vec{j} + V_z \cdot \vec{k})}{\sqrt{(V_x^2 + V_y^2 + V_z^2)}} \quad (6)$$

Where V_x, V_y, V_z are velocities in the x, y and z directions respectively. The unit tangent vector is given by

$$\vec{T} = \frac{T_1 \vec{i} + T_2 \vec{j} + T_3 \vec{k}}{\sqrt{T_1^2 + T_2^2 + T_3^2}} \quad (7)$$

Where $T_1 = \frac{\partial x}{\partial t}, T_2 = \frac{\partial y}{\partial t}, T_3 = \frac{\partial z}{\partial t}$

Equating (6) and (7):

$$\begin{aligned} V_x &= \frac{f_t}{h_t} V_z \\ V_y &= \frac{g_t}{h_t} V_z \\ V_z &= M(u, q, t) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

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In essence, a kinematically-admissible velocity field must satisfy the incompressibility (volume constancy) condition, velocity continuity conditions at entry and exit and boundary conditions at the roll-workpiece interface.

Assuming the deforming material flows according to the Levy-Mises rule and obeys the Mises yield criteria [17], incompressibility condition in three dimensional metal flow can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial V_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial V_z}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (9)$$

Replacing V_x , V_y and V_z from (8) into (9) and solving for $M(u, q, t)$:

$$M = \frac{C \cdot h_t}{h_t (f_u g_q - f_q g_u) + h_q (f_t g_u - f_u g_t) + h_u (f_q g_t - f_t g_q)} \quad (10)$$

Where C is a constant to be determined from the specific continuity conditions at the entry and exit surfaces of each section under study. Velocities calculated using (10) automatically satisfy both the incompressibility and continuity conditions (they were derived from these conditions). Velocity boundary conditions at the roll-workpiece interface are addressed on a case-by-case basis for each rolling operation studied.

Upper bound on rolling power

Once the kinematically-admissible velocity field is found, the total power dissipation for the metal forming process can be calculated. At this stage, the velocity field and power dissipation relations include unknown variables derived from the streamline formulation. As predicted power is inherently greater than the actual value required for the process, continuous minimization of power with respect to unknown variables of the velocity field will give a rolling power value that is as close to the actual value as

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possible. The calculated rolling power can then be used to find rolling torque, average roll pressure and force.

The minimization process will also yield the unknown variables in the velocity field formulation, which can be used to establish the true shape of streamlines and metal flow distribution.

The total power W required to deform the material in a rolling operation is expressed as the sum of the following components: the power required to deform the material plastically, W_i ; the power required to overcome shear forces resulting from velocity discontinuities at entry, W_e , and exit, W_x ; and the power required to overcome friction, W_f . In mathematical terms:

$$W = W_i + W_e + W_x + W_f \quad (11)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} W_i &= \frac{2\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_V (\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{ij})^{1/2} dV \\ W_e &= \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_{A_e} V_e \cdot dA_e \\ W_x &= \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_{A_x} V_x \cdot dA_x \\ W_f &= \frac{m \cdot \bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_{A_f} V_f \cdot dA_f \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

m , $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}$ represent friction shear coefficient, flow stress of the rolled material and strain rates, respectively. Subscripts e, x and f represent entry, exit and surfaces where friction occurs, i.e., the roll-workpiece interface, respectively.

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Using the parametric notation employed in this study, the plastic deformation

component of the total rolling power may be expressed as follows:

$$W_i = \frac{2\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2}{2} + \dot{\epsilon}_{xy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yz}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zx}^2 \right)^{1/2} |J| \cdot dudqdt \quad (13)$$

$\dot{\epsilon}_{xx} \dots$ are strain rates in various directions, $\bar{\sigma}$ is the flow stress and $|J|$ is the Jacobian

for transformation of coordinates from x, y, z to u, q, t .

The velocity discontinuity components of total rolling power can be expressed as

follows. At entry:

$$W_e = \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 (V_x^2 + V_y^2)^{1/2} \frac{\partial(x, y)}{\partial(u, q)} \Big|_{t=0} dudq \quad (14)$$

At exit:

$$W_x = \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 (V_x^2 + V_y^2)^{1/2} \frac{\partial(x, y)}{\partial(u, q)} \Big|_{t=1} dudq \quad (15)$$

The friction component:

$$W_f = \frac{m\bar{\sigma}}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \sqrt{(V_t - V_r)^2 + V_y^2} \Big|_{u=1} \cdot \sec \alpha \cdot \frac{\partial(x, z)}{\partial(q, t)} \Big|_{u=1} \cdot dq \cdot dt \quad (16)$$

Where

$$\sec \alpha = \frac{\sqrt{(N_1^2 + N_2^2 + N_3^2)}}{N_2} \text{ and } \vec{N} = \frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial q} \Big|_{u=1} \times \frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial t} \Big|_{u=1}, \quad V_t = \sqrt{V_x^2 + V_z^2} \text{ and } V_r \text{ is the}$$

tangential roll velocity.

Simulation of Pass Sequences

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The analytical model presented earlier has been employed to simulate single oval-to-round and rectangle-to-diamond passes.

A – Oval-to-round pass

The oval-to-round pass is the most widely used rolling process for the production of round bars. Figure 2 shows the three dimensional deformation zone for the rolling of an oval billet to a round bar. The lower roll has been omitted for clarity. As the rolling geometry is assumed to be symmetrical, a quarter of the deformation zone suffices for the purpose of this analysis. Figure 3 depicts a quarter of the deformation zone for the oval to round pass.

Fig. 2- Three dimensional deformation zone in the single oval-to-round rolling pass

Solid grooved rolls draw the billet inside the roll gap and reduce its cross section (Fig. 2). The projected length of the deformation zone z_0 (Fig. 3) is calculated using the geometrical particulars of the pass and billet dimensions.

This analysis requires an analytical representation of the three dimensional roll groove surface. Assuming that the curve defining the exit cross section of the rolls is $y = f(x)$; every point on the roll groove surface is generated by the rotation of a corresponding point on the curve about the upper roll axis $y = y_c$. The three dimensional roll groove surface may therefore be expressed as:

$$(y_c - f(x))^2 = (y - y_c)^2 + (z_0 - z)^2 \quad (17)$$

y and z are the coordinates of a rotated point on the roll groove surface.

Fig. 3- A quarter of the oval-to-round pass deformation zone

The entry cross section for the oval to round pass is an ellipse with major and minor axes of lengths $2a$ and $2b$, respectively. The exit cross section is a circle with radius r .

The entry and exit cross sections are shown in Fig. 4.

For the purpose of this study, a single Bezier curve was found to be sufficient to appropriately describe the entire deformation zone.

The parametric Bezier formulation for any streamline, e.g. BB' (Fig.1), within the deformation zone in the oval-to-round pass may be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{V}_0 &= ua \sin \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + ub \cos \varphi \cdot \vec{j} \\
 \vec{V}_1 &= a_1 ua \sin \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + b_1 ub \cos \varphi \cdot \vec{j} + c_1 z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}_2 &= a_2 ur \sin \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + b_2 ur \cos \varphi \cdot \vec{j} + c_2 z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}_3 &= ur \sin \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + ur \cos \varphi \cdot \vec{j} + z_0 \cdot \vec{k}
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Where $\phi = \frac{\pi q}{2}$ describes the angular position of the control point \vec{V}_3 . \vec{V}_0 was also determined from the geometry of rolling and the incompressibility condition.

Fig. 4- Entry and exit cross sections in oval-to-round shape rolling

The expressions for the Bezier in parametric terms and in the Cartesian coordinate system are the same as described in the Theory. The vector \vec{r} provides a parametric definition of all the streamlines in the deformation zone. The relation includes 6 unknown coefficients; a_1 to c_2 which will be determined by the optimization of the total power required.

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The velocity field was determined from the procedure expounded in the Theory, then applying the velocity boundary conditions at entry and exit and the incompressibility condition. In the case of oval-to-round shape rolling, constant C from the expression for velocity components along X, Y and Z axes (10) becomes

$$C = \frac{\pi V_e a b u}{2} \quad (19)$$

V_e is the velocity of the oval billet at entry.

The velocity field thus found satisfies both the incompressibility and velocity continuity conditions. To ensure that velocity boundary conditions at the roll-workpiece interface are also met, a subsidiary constraint was imposed; streamlines located on the roll-workpiece interface must also be located on the roll surface. In mathematical terms, this requires that when $u = 1$, the parametric expression of the curve satisfy the three dimensional roll surface equation (17).

A computer code was generated to perform calculations and the optimization process. The optimization process was carried out as follows. The relation for the total rolling power W was found as outlined earlier. This relation contained unknown variables, e.g. a_1 to c_2 , which were determined from the minimization of W. Since the upper bound method provides an upper-limit approximation of the total power required to complete the rolling process, minimization gives a value as close to the required power as possible. Minimization was carried out using the Genetic Algorithm incorporated into the computer program.

Evidently, the minimization process also produces W from which other parameters, torque and pressure, were calculated.

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B – Rectangle-to-diamond pass

The rectangle-to-diamond pass is among the most important shape rolling operations. It is in fact both the final and intermediate pass in the production of square billets. Figure 5 shows a quarter of the deformation zone in the rolling of a rectangular billet to a diamond cross section.

Fig. 5- A quarter of the deformation zone in a single rectangle-to-diamond pass

It has been assumed that the entry cross section is a rectangular cross section $2w_0$ wide and $2h_0$ high. The exit cross section is rhomboidal with a large diameter of $2a$ and a small diameter of $2b$. Unlike oval-to-round shape rolling, in the rectangle-to-diamond pass the deformation zone was found to be too complex to be appropriately described by a single Bezier curve. The deformation zone was therefore divided in two sections as shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. For each section one Bezier curve and one set of velocity field formulae were developed.

Fig. 6- Entry and exit cross sections in first half of the deformation zone in the rectangle-to-diamond pass

Fig. 7- Entry and exit cross sections in second half of the deformation zone in the rectangle-to-diamond pass

In the first section:

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{V}_0 &= uh_0 \operatorname{tg} \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + uh_0 \cdot \vec{j} \\
 \vec{V}_1 &= a_1 uh_0 \operatorname{tg} \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + b_1 uh_0 \cdot \vec{j} + c_1 z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}_2 &= a_2 a \frac{h_0}{2w_0} \operatorname{tg} \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + b_2 u \frac{b(2w_0 - h_0 \operatorname{tg} \varphi)}{2w_0} \cdot \vec{j} + c_2 z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}_3 &= ua \frac{h_0}{2w_0} \operatorname{tg} \varphi \cdot \vec{i} + u \frac{b(2w_0 - h_0 \operatorname{tg} \varphi)}{2w_0} \cdot \vec{j} + z_0 \cdot \vec{k}
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

$\varphi = \frac{\pi q}{4}$ marks the angular position of the entry streamlines. Parametric and Cartesian

expressions are the same as discussed earlier.

In the second section:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{V}'_0 &= uw_0 \cdot \vec{i} + uw_0 \operatorname{tg} \varphi \cdot \vec{j} \\
 \vec{V}'_1 &= a'_1 uw_0 \cdot \vec{i} + b'_1 uw_0 \operatorname{tg} \varphi \cdot \vec{j} + c'_1 z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}'_2 &= a'_2 ua \left(\frac{2h_0 - w_0 \operatorname{tg} \varphi}{2h_0} \right) \cdot \vec{i} + b'_2 ub \frac{w_0 \operatorname{tg} \varphi}{2h_0} \cdot \vec{j} + c'_2 z_0 \cdot \vec{k} \\
 \vec{V}'_3 &= ua \left(\frac{2h_0 - w_0 \operatorname{tg} \varphi}{2h_0} \right) \cdot \vec{i} + ub \frac{w_0 \operatorname{tg} \varphi}{2h_0} \cdot \vec{j} + z_0 \cdot \vec{k}
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

The velocity field in both halves was derived using previous relations. The constant C in the expression for velocity components along X, Y and Z axes (10) becomes in the first half

$$C = \frac{\pi u V_e h_0^2}{4 \cos^2 \left(\frac{\pi q}{4} \right)} \tag{22}$$

And in the second:

$$C = \frac{-\pi u V_e w_0^2}{4 \cos^2 \left(\frac{\pi q}{4} \right)} \tag{23}$$

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The velocities derived satisfy both the incompressibility and the velocity continuity conditions. To ensure that velocity boundary conditions at the roll-workpiece interface are also met, the first subsidiary constraint mentioned earlier was imposed. As the analysis involves two sections, a second condition was imposed to secure continuity of velocity at the interface of the two sections. In mathematical terms, this requires that when $q = 1$, $\bar{r}(u, q, t) = \bar{r}'(u, q, t)_{q=1}$. The relation must be true for all u and t . The rectangle-to-diamond analysis contains 12 unknown variables which will be determined by the optimization of the total rolling power in much the same manner as previously discussed.

Results and discussion

The single-pass rolling of oval-to-round and rectangle-to-diamond was simulated using the formulation presented in this paper. The results obtained from these simulations are as discussed as follows:

A – Oval-to-round

The oval-to-round pass was evaluated against the experiment/analysis carried out by [3]. Table 1 outlines the conditions adopted for the analysis of the oval-to-round pass.

Table 1- Conditions adopted for the analysis of a single pass oval-to-round sequence

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Oval-to-round pass sequence	Analytical Conditions
Entry cross section dimensions	2a = 28.3mm, 2b = 32.9mm
Exit cross section dimensions	r = 12.7mm
Area reduction	17%
Roll gap	1.58mm
Roll tangential velocity	254mm/sec

The material used was low carbon steel – AISI 1018 – and rolling assumed to have been carried out at 1090°C in which the flow stress may be described by [3]

$$\bar{\sigma} = 77.5\dot{\epsilon}^{0.192} \text{MPa} \quad (24)$$

Figures 8 to 12 illustrate various cross sections within the deformation zone, from

$\frac{z}{Z_0} = 0$ to $\frac{z}{Z_0} = 1$, as predicted by the present method. In each figure, the cross sectional

shape predicted by [3] has been superimposed for comparison.

Fig. 8- Entry cross section in the oval-to-round pass as predicted by this study and reference [3].

Fig. 9- Intermediate cross section at $\frac{z}{Z_0} = 0.25$ in the oval-to-round pass. Reference [3] is superimposed.

Fig. 10- Intermediate cross section at $\frac{z}{Z_0} = 0.5$ in the oval-to-round pass. Reference [3] is superimposed.

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Fig. 11- Intermediate cross section at $\frac{Z}{Z_0} = 0.75$ in the oval-to-round pass. Reference [3] is superimposed.

Fig. 12- Exit cross section in the oval-to-round pass as predicted by this study and reference [3]

It can be observed from Fig. 8 to 12 that in all cases the present study predicts a cross section closer to the actual roll surface than reference [3]. Due to the streamline formulation, the present analysis predicts a curved, continuous upper surface while reference [3] includes a flat upper side.

Several roll pass dimensions constituting various area reduction values ($q = 1 - \frac{A_{ex}}{A_e}$) were considered to investigate the effect of area reduction and frictional conditions on roll torque. It should be noted that for a given rolling operation with specific rolling conditions, the friction shear factor (m) is a constant, the amount of which is determined from experiments, most famously the ring test. However, for the purposes of this study, different friction shear conditions ($m=0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.75$) were assumed to clarify the effect of friction on rolling as illustrated in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13- The effect of friction on roll torque in various area reduction values

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The effect of friction and area reduction values on the average roll pressure to flow stress ratio is shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14- The effect of friction on average rolling pressure to flow stress ratio in various area reduction values

It can be seen from Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 that both the roll torque and the average roll pressure to flow stress ratio increase with increasing reduction and friction factor values, in effect requiring greater rolling power. The friction factor directly affects the power required to overcome friction forces and thus the total rolling power. The influence of reduction is more subtle, influencing both entry and exit cross section dimensions, velocity fields and all the components of power required for rolling.

The oval-to-round pass was also compared against the analytical method proposed by Bayoumi [6] and part of the experiment carried out in Reference [2]. This experiment includes a four-step round-to-oval-to-round-to-oval-to-round rolling sequence, and the present analysis was used to simulate the intermediate round-to-oval sequences.

Low-carbon AISI-1080 steel was taken as the rolling material, rolling temperature was assumed to be 1090°C and flow stress was found to be similar to 27. Table 2 outlines the dimensions adopted for the two simulated sequences.

Table 3 shows average rolling power and exit velocity as determined by the flow-line field solution in [6], experiment [2] and the upper bound method by the authors. Good agreement was found between experimental results and the results from this study, although the present method slightly overestimates power and velocity due to the inherent tendency of the upper bound method.

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The major advantage of the proposed upper bound method over the flowline field solution is that, with slight alteration of formulation and with varying degrees of complexity, the upper bound approach is applicable to almost all shape rolling operations. The flowline field solution on the other hand is limited to the round-oval-round rolling sequence (of which the oval-to-round pass has been included in Table 3 for purposes of comparison). It is also evident from Table 3 that average rolling pressure values obtained from the upper bound method are closer to experimental data compared to values obtained from the flowline solution.

Table 2- Rolling dimensions and conditions adopted for the intermediate oval-to-round passes of a four-step round-to-round rolling sequence [2,6]

Pass sequence number	2	4
Pass geometry	Oval-to-round	Oval-to-round
Exit cross section dimensions	Φ20.1 mm	Φ14.2 mm
Entry cross section dimensions (major axis×minor axis)	148×43 mm ²	30.1×10.4 mm ²
Roll center distance	280 mm	280 mm
Area reduction	36.51%	35.5%
Rotational speed	105 rpm	198.5 rpm
Roll gap	2.5mm	2mm

Table 3- Average rolling pressure and exit velocity calculated from the present study compared to actual experiment [2] and the flowline field solution [6]

Pass No. 2	Pass No. 4
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	Friction factor m	Average rolling pressure P_{av} (MPa)	Difference from experiment %	Billet exit velocity V_{ex} (m/s)	Friction factor m	Average rolling pressure P_{av} (MPa)	Difference from experiment %	Billet exit velocity V_{ex} (m/s)
Experiment [2]	0.468	113.8	0	1.458	0.378	136.2	0	2.903
Upper Bound Method (authors)	0.468	116.6	2.46	1.507	0.378	141.9	4.18	3.022
Flowline field method [6]	0.468	106	-6.85	1.493	0.378	120	-11.8	2.899

The effect of increasing friction shear factor on roll torque for both simulated sequences is shown in Fig. 15 and Fig. 16, which also show the results from [6]. Again, agreement was found between the two sets of results, with the same slight overestimation for the upper bound method.

Fig. 15- The effect of increasing friction shear factor on roll torque for pass no. 2 determined from the authors' upper bound method and the flowline field solution [6]

Fig. 16- The effect of increasing friction shear factor on roll torque for pass no. 4 determined from the authors' upper bound method and the flowline field solution [6]

B – Rectangle-to-diamond pass

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The rectangle-to-diamond simulation was carried out under conditions extracted from an analytical solution attempted in [5]. The analysis assumes cold (temperature 15°C) rolling of a Pb-0.9%wt-Sb alloy whose flow stress is expressed by

$$\bar{\sigma} = 49.3\bar{\epsilon}^{0.04}\bar{\epsilon}^{-0.25}\text{MPa} \quad (25)$$

Other conditions adopted for this analysis are shown in Table 4.

Table 4- Conditions adopted for the analysis of the single rectangle-to-diamond pass

Rectangle-to Diamond			
Rolling Temperature	Roll Velocity	Roll Diameter	Incoming Billet Dimensions
15°C	20 RPM	50mm	Length: 300mm Thickness: 10mm Width: 15, 20, 25mm

The effect of increasing friction shear factor values on roll torque and roll average pressure to flow stress ratio with different area reduction values was investigated in Fig. 17, Fig. 18. As seen from the figures, both rolling torque and roll average pressure to flow stress ratio values increase with increasing reduction of area and friction shear factor. The most demanding rolling operations in terms of power requirement are those which have the greatest area reduction and friction shear factor values. As rolling pressure and torque are calculated directly from total rolling power, higher roll torque and pressure are required for higher friction and area reduction values. It should be mentioned that no experimental or analytical solution capable of predicting roll torque or rolling pressure in the diamond-to-rectangle pass was available and therefore no comparison has been made.

Fig. 17- The effect of friction on roll torque with various area reduction values

Fig. 18- The effect of friction on average rolling pressure to flow stress ration with various area reduction values

Conclusions

A method has been proposed to analyze metal deformation, roll torque, average roll pressure and exit velocity for the shape rolling of geometrical entities without protrusions.

The authors have made the following conclusions from the comparison between the results obtained from this analysis and experimental/analytical studies from other works:

- The shape rolling analysis presented is capable of accurately predicting metal flow patterns, despite the increasing difficulty of solution for cross sections that are geometrically complex.
- The shape rolling analysis presented is capable of accurately predicting roll torque and average roll pressure. However, compared to experiments, the upper bound method somewhat overestimates torque and pressure. In actual practice, though, this is considered an advantage since these slightly higher values ensure the feasibility of the rolling operation.

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- For sections in which the deforming material initiates contact with the roll groove surface toward the outer edge of the entry cross section, such as the rectangle-to-diamond pass, additional parameters are required to allow an accurate representation of the deformation zone. In contrast, passes in which contact is initiated toward the inner edges of the entry cross section, such as the oval-to-round pass, are simpler to analyze. The additional parameters entail inclusion of additional surfaces and curves, complicating the analysis and slowing convergence to optimum. The upper bound analysis is therefore less accurate than that for the sections which initiate contact toward the inner edges.

- The method presented obviates the need for complicated and, in most cases computationally overpowering, FEM simulation of the rolling passes. Whereas other analytical solutions are limited to the specific passes they are developed for, the upper bound method presented is capable of analyzing various cross sections with simple modification of streamline formulation. The method presented also has the potential for further expansion to include other rolling passes as well as other metal forming operations.

- The formulation presented could be the basis of commercially-developed software to predict power, pressure, torque and forces required for an industrial shape rolling process.

References

[1] Lange, K., 1985, *Handbook of Metal Forming*, McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York.

[2] Wusatowski, Z., 1969, *Fundamentals of Rolling*, Pergamon Press, New York.

Pre-print of: [Karen Abrinia](#) & A. Fazlirad (2010). Investigation of Single Pass Shape Rolling Using an Upper Bound Method. *Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance*. DOI: [10.1007/s11665-009-9511-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-009-9511-x)

[3] Kennedy, K. F., 1986, "A Method for Metal Deformation and Stress Analysis in Rolling," PhD thesis, Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio.

[4] Hill, R., 1963, "A General Method of Analysis for Metal Deformation Processes," *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, **11**, pp. 305-326.

[5] Saito, Y., Kusumoto, Y., Hattori, T., and Kato, K., 1984, "Deformation Analysis in Shape Rolling Using an Upper Bound Method," *J. Adv. Technol. Plast.*, **11**, pp. 1190-1199.

[6] Bayoumi, L. S., 1998, "Flow and Stresses in Round-Oval-Round Pass Sequence," *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, **40**(12), pp. 1223-1234.

[7] Oh, S. I., and Kobayashi, S., 1975, "An Approximate Method for a Three-Dimensional Analysis of Rolling," *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, **17**, pp. 293–305.

[8] Kim, N., Lee, S., Shin, W., and Shivpuri, R., 1992, "Simulation of Square-to-Oval Single Pass Rolling Using a Computationally Effective Finite and Slab Element Method," *ASME J. Eng. Ind.*, **114**, pp. 329-335.

[9] Lee, S., Shin, W., and Shivpuri, R., 1992, "Investigation of Two Square-to-Round Multipass Rolling Sequences by the Slab-Finite Element Method," *Int. J. Mach. Tools Manuf.*, **32**(3), pp. 315-327.

[10] Park, J. J., and Oh, S. I., 1990, "Application of Three Dimensional Finite Element Analysis to Shape Rolling Processes," *ASME J. Eng. Ind.*, **112**, pp. 36–46.

[11] Mori, K., and Osakada, K., 1991, "Non-Steady-State Simulation of Three-Dimensional Deformation Around Front and Rear Ends in Shape Rolling by the Finite Element Method," *Transactions of NAMRI/SME*, **19**, pp. 9-14.

[12] Mori, K., and Osakada, K., 1993, "FEM Simulator With Mesh Generator for Shape Rolling," *Transactions of NAMRI/SME*, **21**, pp. 9–15.

Pre-print of: [Karen Abrinia](#) & A. Fazlirad (2010). Investigation of Single Pass Shape Rolling Using an Upper Bound Method. *Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance*. DOI: [10.1007/s11665-009-9511-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-009-9511-x)

[13] Kim, N., Kobayashi, S., and Altan, T., 1992, "Three Dimensional Analysis and Computer Simulation of Shape Rolling by the Finite and Slab Element Method," *Int. J. Mach. Tools Manuf.*, **31**(4), pp. 553–563.

[14] Hsiang, S. H., and Lin, S. L., 2001, "Application of 3D FEM-Slab Method to Shape Rolling," *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, **43**, pp. 1155-1177.

[15] Abrinia, K., 1990, "A Generalised Upper Bound Solution for Three-Dimensional Extrusion of Shaped Sections Using Bilinear and Advanced Surface Dies," PhD thesis, University of Manchester Institute of Science and Technology, Manchester, UK.

[16] Qiulin, D., and Davis, B. J., 1987, *Surface Engineering Geometry for Computer-Aided Design and Manufacture*, Ellis Horwood Ltd., New York.

[17] Johnson, W., and Mellor, P. B., 1983, *Engineering Plasticity*, Ellis Harwood Ltd., New York.